

**Biomimicry of Combative Bovids to Revamp a
Lightweight, Energy-Absorbing Lattice for High Impact
Applications**

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Abstract

Muskox (*Ovibos moschatus*) and big horn sheep (*Ovis canadensis*) participate in forceful head-butting clashes without getting a permanent traumatic brain injury. The big horn sheep horncore is composed of velar bone architecture covered by keratin sheaths, enabling it to absorb significant strain energy. The muskox skull relies on multilayer composition of keratin, trabecular and cortical bone to endure the massive cranial impact estimated by 12,500 N. Previous studies have found the horncore of the big horn sheep stores three times more strain energy than the horn. Additionally, the horn-like truss lattice showed a higher energy absorption than other type of lattices. In the current study, the horn shape of the muskox was merged with the horn-inspired flower-like lattice to create a lightweight, energy absorbing lattice. The objective is to investigate the role of external horns (points of impact) on the overall energy absorption. Two designs were modelled, one with external horns and one without, and 3D-printed using PLA+ plastic and tested under repeated impact force. The lattice with points of impact absorbed 31% of the total energy of impact while the one without absorbed 25%. The study found that the points of impact are only effective with ductile materials. In addition, material ductility and toughness are more critical in the energy absorption than structural geometry.

Introduction

Combative bovids engage in powerful head-to-head strikes to establish dominance and claim mating rights during the rut. Muskox (*Ovibos moschatus*) and big horn sheep (*Ovis canadensis*) exemplify this the best. The big horn sheep can engage in intense head-butting combat for several hours per day (Aguirre et al.). The big horn sheep's head can experience a force exceeding 3400 N per strike (Maity and Tekalur) and a sudden deceleration of impact occurs over less than 300 ms (Farke). The muskox can exceed 400 kg in mass and strikes at a speed around 30 mph (Ackermans). Furthermore, they can survive these impacts without obvious brain injury (Fuller and Donahue).

The big horn sheep's horn is composed of bony horncore covered by keratin. It can endure bending stresses ranging from 1 to 6 MPa in tension and 1 to 7 MPa in compression (Aguirre et al.). The unique architecture of the horncore absorbs three times more strain energy than the horn during impact (Aguirre et al.). The horncore is made up of velar bone, a foam-like structure, which differs from the normal rod-like bone structure of trabecular bone (Aguirre et al.). This gives the horns the minimum weight to be durable enough to prevent rupture in the middle of a fight (Kitchener).

The geometry of the horn plays an important role in strain dissipation and decreases the brain cavity acceleration. Some of the energy dissipates through medial-lateral horn tip oscillations post-impact (Wheatley et al.). Finite element analysis (FEA) showed that the horn structure reduces formation of a head injury by 48% compared to horns with cross-sections rotated by 90° to have a cranial-caudal bending preference (Wheatley et al.).

The muskoxen encounter much stronger strikes, a simulation for the headbutting estimates the force to be over 12500 N (Snively and Theodor). The muskox's head depends on multilayer composition of various properties, including a thick tough keratin, followed with

trabecular bone and cortical bone (*Multiscale Investigation of Impact Mitigation Strategies: Biomimicking Muskox Head*).

The velar bone architecture is too complicated to be designed without CT (computed tomography). Rather, trusses can be used as an approximation for velar bone's architecture; the velar bone depends on individual's thickness and more spacing unlike trabecular bone (Aguirre et al.). Tapering and curvature are distinctive qualities in horns and proved a high energy absorption and impact mitigation (Zhou et al.). The previous studies focused on mimicking the velar bone structure or creating a lattice inspired by the shape of the horn. However, none of them used points of impact (external horns) to reduce post-impact force or used any of the muskox's unique properties.

Biomimicry of big horn sheep and muskox will not only produce a high energy absorbent structure with minimum deformation but also have a lightweight and optimized design. The new design can be used in various applications including crumple zones.

Crumple zones were created in 1959 by Bèla Barènyi, and first used by Mercedes-Benz (Day, "Crumple Zones"). The design consists of a weak cell on the front and back of the car to protect the rigid, strong occupants' cell in the center. However, a WHO report estimated 1.19 million die annually from car accidents, while 20-50 million others suffer from non-fatal injuries (World Health Organization: WHO). Furthermore, traffic crashes cost the US alone about \$340 billion in 2019 ("NHTSA: Traffic Crashes").

The aim of this study is to merge the main characteristics of muskox and big horn sheep to make a lightweight horn-like lattice, and to investigate the effect of point of impact on the energy absorption through testing on a 3D-printed model.

Methods

2.1 Design process

Figure 1: On the right, mimicking the horn to make a truss. On the left, A horn-inspired flower-like structure made on SolidWorks. source of the image on the left: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17452759.2025.2524525>.

The design of the lattice went through multiple steps. First, the horn-inspired flower-like structure from big horn sheep, as shown in Figure 1, used as an approximation for the trusses

Figure 2: On the left, horn core longitudinal-section showing the architecture of velar bone foam-like structure. Depends on individual thickness other than the density unlike normal trabecular bone. On the right, normal trabecular bone. Source <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2016.08.019>.

in the velar bone structure, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 3: On the right, the sandwich lattice structure of four layers. On the left, dimensions of the flower like lattice. Designed on SolidWorks 2021.

It proved its effectiveness against other types of lattices like kelvin and G7 lattices (Babu et al.). Sandwich structures are better in testing the lattices performance on energy absorption (Shen et al.).

The sandwich-lattice structure was designed on SolidWorks 2021 (by Dassault Systemes) using linear patterns for the flower-like structure. Then, another linear pattern to complete the four layers and produced a binary mesh of over seven million triangles. Then, the mesh was reduced to 70,000 triangles through Rhino 8 (by Robert McNeel & Associates). The design consists of four layers with 3x5 flower-like structure. The horn-like shape is about 10mm in height and 14mm in depth. The entire structure is 60mm in height, 48mm in width and 77mm in length.

A typical design was made with a few adjustments to the lattice. On the top of the sandwich, a muskox-like horn was designed, as shown in Figure 4. A small bull horn used as a point of impact to see how it would affect the total energy absorption and post-impact mitigation.

Figure 4: On the right, Muskox skull. On the left, the design of lattice with external horns to act like points of impact. Source of the image on the right: www.skullsite.co.uk/Muskox/muskox.htm.

2.2 Manufacturing process

To get the best results from 3D-printing, the design was separated into independent layers, as shown in Figure 5, and then fixed together with super glue. Furthermore, a small, circular base is used under each flower for greater stability. The design was printed on ELEGOO Neptune 4 pro and using PLA+ (Polylactic Acid Plus) filament. It has a density of 1.23 g/cm^3 , tensile strength of 63 MPa and 20% elongation at break (Shenzhen Esun Industrial Co., Ltd.). Printed layers are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: On the top, the first layer of the 3D-printed lattice. On the bottom, a preview for the layers before printing

2.3 Examination and testing

To simulate a real-world accident, the impact force used to see the energy absorption for the different designs. 340g-hammer was dropped from 30cm on the lattices four times. A 30cm-long ruler put beside the designs to calculate the deformation, as shown in Figure 6. A slow-motion video was filmed with normal ratio and slowed with a 95% using Adobe Premiere Pro. The lattice without horns weighed 50g and the one with weighted 55g.

Figure 6: An image for the destruction of the lattice

Calculations

Energy absorption is the integration of the stress-strain curve, which can be calculated with $F_{avg}(D_f - D_i)$, where F_{avg} is the average force of impact, D_f is the final crushing displacement (Al-Qrimli et al.). It can be calculated also as numerical integration $F_1 \times D_1 + F_2 \times D_2 + \dots + F_n \times D_n$. The total energy can be calculated by Mgh , where M is mass, g is gravity and h is the height. The total energy is $0.34 \times 0.3 \times 9.8 \approx 1$ J. The lattice without external horns experienced four drops all from 30cm, so the total energy is 4 J. The total deformation in the lattice was about 2cm. The impact force can be calculated by $F = M \times a$, where a is the acceleration during impact. The acceleration can be determined by a kinematic equation, $v^2 = u^2 + 2as$, where v is the final velocity (which is zero after impact), u is the initial velocity and s the total displacement (the total deformation). The initial velocity (the velocity at impact) is $\sqrt{2gh} = \sqrt{2 \times 9.8 \times 0.3} \approx 2.42$.

Substituting in the equation

$$0 = 2.42^2 + 2 \times a \times 0.02. \quad -5.86 = 0.04a. \quad a = -146.5 \text{ m/s}^2$$

Substituting again in $F = M \times a$, $F = 0.34 \times -146.5 \approx 50N$

The total energy absorption (TEA)= $50 \times 0.02 = 0.996J$

The specific energy absorption is (SEA) is measured by the TEA/mass and have SI unit kJ/kg. The lattice weighs about 50 grams, the SEA is $\frac{0.001}{0.05} = 0.02$.

The lattice with external horns experienced the same amount of force on the same height and got a total deformation of about 2.5cm. The TEA is $50 \times 0.025 = 1.25\text{J}$, and the SEA is $\frac{0.00125}{0.055} \approx 0.023$ kJ/kg.

Results

The lattice without horns absorbed about 1J of energy out of 4J, absorbing 25% of the total energy. On the other hand, the lattice horns absorbed 1.25J out of 4J, absorbing about 31% of the total energy. The EA values are shown in Figure 7. The specific energy absorption for the lattice without horns is 0.02 kJ/kg and 0.023 kJ/kg for the lattice with horns. Upon crashing, both lattices showed a catastrophic failure. The lateral tips of the flower-like structures were shattered on impact and scattered all around.

Figure 7: The energy absorption (EA) in both the lattice with horns and without horn

The energy absorption per each drop for the lattice without horns are shown in Figure 8.

The lattice deformation was the maximum on the first impact, about 0.7cm, followed by 0.4, 0.5 and finally 0.4, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 8: On the Energy absorbed (EA) per each drop for the lattice without horn.

Exp.num	Force	displacement	EA	SEA
1	50	0.007	0.35	1
2	50	0.004	0.2	
3	50	0.005	0.25	
4	50	0.004	0.2	

Figure 9: Table of the data for the lattice without horns

The horn-inspired flower-like structure was more flattened in the lattice with horns, as shown in Figure 10. The lattices after 4 impacts are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 10: On the right, the flower structure of the lattice with horns. On the left, the flower structure of the lattice without horns.

Figure 11: Lattices after destruction. On the right, the lattice with horns. On the left, the lattice without horns.

Analysis

The experimental results demonstrated a higher storage capacity for the lattice with the improved design, where it could absorb 6% more energy, supporting the thesis of this research. While the specific energy absorption is low for a dedicated absorber (0.023 kJ/kg for the lattice with horns, 0.02 kJ/kg for the lattice without one), it was more likely due to the brittle characteristics of the plastic. The following analysis will interpret the data.

5.1 Difference in rupture between lattices

The points of impact (horns) can dissipate post-impact energy through oscillations in the horns of both big horn sheep and muskox. A finite element analysis (FEM), as shown in Figure 12, found that the lateral tips of horns hold the greatest stress in the musk ox (Foucher et al.). In the lattice with points of impact, the horns work as an initial contact point, transmitting a part of the energy to the horns and concentrating the force in a small area; which resulted in slow, progressive collapse and lower energy diffusion through layers; which led to a 6% increase in absorption.

Figure 12: Principal natural mode shape of the muskox skull at ~250 Hz, excited by an impact on the horn. Source: https://www.conftool.com/esb2025/index.php/ESB2025_4.1_6_Foucher.pdf?page=downloadPaper&filename=ESB2025_4.1_6_Foucher.pdf&form_id=904

The rupture process was quite similar in both lattices, an instant rupture occurred in the center layers and stress enhancers (cracks) initiated in the other layers, which initiated an uneven force distribution, leading to their destruction on later impacts. The last layer failed due to the fatigue and was the last to get destroyed, the other layers were completely destroyed or heavily damaged before the fourth drop. The bottom layer was more preserved in the lattice with horn, as shown in Figure 13. The force did not diffuse to the last layer as the upper

layers dissipate energy before reaching the last one, which is optimal for crumple zones, providing the maximum protection for occupants.

Figure 13: On the right, the lattice with horns did not diffuse the energy to the final layer after 3 impacts, which make it optimal for high impact applications and crumple zones. On the left, the lattice without horns diffuses the force to the last layer, which is not the best for users' safety.

5.2 Ductility of materials

Material toughness and ductility are the essential factors for the energy absorption and specific energy absorption, and it is more probable to be critical than structural geometry in specific energy absorption (SEA). The resulted low SEA could be raised by using a ductile plastic like acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene (ABS). It shows a ductile behaviour on failure (Wainstein et al.) and can be used in 3D-printers. It was not implemented in this study for its relative high cost.

PLA+ plastic is used since it is affordable, cost-effective and could be used in various types of 3D-printers. Nevertheless, it's brittle and show a catastrophic failure on rupture and did not exhibit a plastic deformation. Rather, the flower-like structures broke on impact or initiated cracks. It's suggested that the points of impact are not so effective in brittle materials.

5.3 Horn's curvature & number of layers

Both lattices are 4 layers each. The four layers are trapped between five sandwich sheets; its thickness is 0.5 cm per individual. That results in incompressible 2.5 cm and merely diffuses the energy to layers beneath. Hence, decreasing the number of layers and increasing the length, within the same height, of individual flower-like structures would escalate the energy absorption (EA).

The tapered and curved tips of the flower was the first to deform or break at impact, owing to the presence of torque on the curved tip that ease its deformation or rupture. On the other hand, the roots of the flower experience roughly perpendicular force, making it more difficult to break and tends to diffuse the force. Thus, lengthening the flower and increasing curvature angle would revamp the SEA and EA.

Conclusion

This research aimed to investigate the effect of points of impact and an improved lattice design on the energy absorption. This study implemented a tapered and curved horn-inspired flower-like structure in the internal lattice, and muskox-like horns used as points of impact. Two lattices were designed, 3D-printed and tested under repeated impact force. The lattice with points of impacts absorbed 31% of the total energy of impact and the lattice without one absorbed 25% of the total energy.

The findings showed that the points of impact are dependent on the toughness of the material. The integration of external horn-like points of impact enhanced the energy absorption by 6% using PLA+ plastic. This suggests that points of impact would dissipate more energy in

ductile materials. Moreover, the ductility and toughness are more critical than the structure geometry alone.

The increased tapering and curvature in the lateral tips of horns elevate the energy absorption. Further, fewer layers in a bounding height suggests a reduction in the acceleration during impact in addition to higher energy storage.

Those findings highlight the potential of using such lattice with points of impact in high-impact applications, such as crumple zones, sports armours and driving helmets. This study was limited by simplified testing methods, lack of access to advanced meshing technologies and the use of PLA+ plastic in prototyping, hindering a direct scalability and a comparable result to crumple zones.

Future work

The lattice developed in this research may be used as an energy absorbing layer in crumple zones using copper for its ductility, positioned between two tough materials like in the front and rear chassis. Moreover, it is recommended to use a computed tomography (CT) to scan and create a mesh that mimics the velar bone architecture; that would raise the energy absorption and mitigate the impact of crashes on occupants.

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